

Approach to Intel Concept

Artur Victoria

The union of intelligence with the knowledge of our own capabilities, and those of our allies, provides the foundation for the planning and execution of operations.

Intelligence today is not only about cataloguing the forces of an adversary and evaluating his capabilities. It also encompasses an understanding of the adversary's culture, motivation, perspective, and goals.

Operational environments

Key actors and threats that define the operational environments: - Terrorism. - Hostile states. - Fragile and failed states. - Hybrid threats. - Globalization. - Environmental and humanitarian. - Proliferation.

The three main areas of impact are: - The complexity of the operations. - Abundance of information. - Dissemination of traditional borders at the tactical, operational and strategic levels.

Intelligence agencies must be able to produce intelligence based on a wide range of factors. To do this they will need to rely on experts to shore up their analyzes or reach-back support (from outside the area of operations) to support managers and organizations, including non-military and non-governmental organizations.

1. Understanding is the perception and interpretation of a particular situation in order to provide the necessary context, point of view and foresight for decision making. This includes answering the main questions who, what, where, when, why and how, which provide the context and narrative of events.

Situation assessment is the general term used when a decision maker at any level has the correct level of understanding and the ability to put new data and information into context to make rational decisions and execute actions.

2. Data and Information and Decision Making.

Information is defined as raw data of all kinds that can be used in intelligence production.

Command intelligence responsibilities.

The ultimate responsibility for intelligence lies in command. The managers must become familiar with the intelligence process and have a sufficient assessment of the situation to articulate their critical information needs. It is the responsibility of the command to provide direction and guidance, define priorities, provide intelligence collection and analysis effectively, demand the highest quality of products and review the effects of their chosen actions.

Command and decision making.

A good manager must know that: - A correlation and interdependence between quality and opportunity is inevitable. - Commanders should not delegate their decisions. - Good decisions are derived from training and experience. - The agencies advise the decision-making of the command and this needs mutual trust between each other.

- Command vision. It is the ability to create a mental image of the future using imagination and wisdom. It provides the context for the development of knowledge at all levels and for determining the level of intelligence support required.

- Command intention. It is the clear and concise expression of command of what the force must do and the conditions it must establish to fulfil its mission.

- Promotion of access to intelligence. Focusing the intelligence effort and achieving dissemination on time will always be a challenge for the command.

- The managers must create an atmosphere that allows an open mind with critical analysis and creative thinking.

General Concept

Intelligence is the product resulting from the direct obtaining and elaboration of information related to the environment and the capacities and intentions of the actors in order to identify threats and offer opportunities for exploitation by decision-makers.

The intelligence combat function includes the set of activities aimed at satisfying the command's knowledge needs, related to the operating environment, necessary for planning and conducting operations, as well as for identifying threats against own forces and compliance of the mission.

It should be categorized based on its intended use.

Consequently, there are three specific definitions of intelligence at these levels:

- Strategic intelligence. Intelligence necessary for the formation of politics, military planning and the provision of signs and alerts, at the national and international level.

- Operational intelligence. Intelligence required for planning and conducting operational level campaigns.
- Tactical intelligence. Intelligence required for planning and executing operations at a tactical level.

The role of intelligence is to contribute to continuous and coordinated knowledge in a complex global environment to facilitate appropriate decisions that allow Managers to take the necessary actions to maintain security. It is an aid to developing understanding and a critical tool for decision making.

Categories

- Basic Intelligence. Intelligence on any matter, which can be used as a material reference for planning and as a basis for developing subsequent information or intelligence. Basic intelligence provides the context and backdrop against which to review current intelligence.
- Current Intelligence. It is the one that reflects the current situation at any level, strategic or tactical. Intelligence reports and summaries provide current intelligence for the Common Operational Picture (COP) and predictions for possible developments.

Principles of Intel

- Accessibility. Intelligence has no value if it is not disseminated, or is accessible, to those who need it.
- Share. There are necessary mechanisms by which intelligence can be shared, in a timely manner. The source of the information must be protected and the information itself must be filtered to protect the source in order to share information with others.
- Answer's capacity. Intelligence agencies must be able to quickly analyze, merge, develop, and present products for military and non-military decision makers.
- Flexibility. Intelligence agencies must establish a representation that provides timely, relevant and focused intelligence designed to evolve with security challenges.
- Interoperability. Common or interoperable processes, networks and systems are necessary to support the direction, acquisition, elaboration and dissemination of intelligence, and the management of the organization of intelligence.
- Integrity. Intelligence must be comprehensive in nature and must explain the interrelated elements of a complex operational environment impartially without distortion.

Attributes

- Intelligence is command-driven. Intelligence is a fundamental responsibility of command.
- Intelligence is collaborative. Intelligence has the ability to draw the skills of a broad spectrum of experts and specialists in a variety of organizations.
- Intelligence is timely. Intelligence must be delivered on time.
- Intelligence is fusion. A multi-source approach uses the concept of intelligence fusion to optimize the value of multiple sources of information.
- Intelligence is objective. Intelligence must always avoid bias, needing organisms with open minds.

Limitations

- Expectations management. Intelligence agencies must be realistic about what can be accomplished through intelligence activity, especially when resources are limited.
- Incomplete intelligence. Intelligence may not exactly meet the needs of command and may not be fully appropriate, complete, or easily corroborated.
- Means of obtaining. All means of obtaining, exploiting and processing have limitations.

Capacities and intentions.

In contemporary and future operational environments, intelligence agencies must ensure that managers understand the increasing difficulty of determining adversarial capabilities, centres of gravity, networks, and intent.

National restrictions.

Under no circumstances should managers or their organizations assign taxpaying nations to carry out activities that are contrary to their laws.

International Legislation.

All intelligence activity must be conducted within this legal framework.

The main functions of intelligence are:

- Development of knowledge and facilitating understanding. Develops knowledge about the environment and the actors, including their intentions, capacities and motivations.

- Production of predictive evaluations. Intelligence must look ahead, making it easier for command to maintain initiative. Regardless, reviewing past and current activities may indicate future intentions and should be used consistently.

Bodies sources and sensors

A source is a person or thing from which information can be obtained. Sources can be divided into controlled, uncontrolled or casual:

- Controlled. Controlled sources are under the control of an intelligence body.
- Uncontrolled. Uncontrolled sources are those that are not under the formal control of an intelligence agency or organization.
- Casual sources. Casual sources provide unsolicited information.

Protection of the source.

Source protection is critical where covert procurement capabilities are involved. However, source protection should not be a reason to retain intelligence.

Organs

An organ is an organization involved in obtaining or processing information. An organ must be able to obtain and elaborate information or it may simply have the capacity to obtain information and pass that information on to another organ for its elaboration.

Sensors

They are entities or parts of equipment that detect, and can indicate and / or record objects and activities through the energy or particles emitted, reflected or modified by objects.

Simple and multiple source intelligence

Most intelligence is derived from a single source. However, there are significant advantages in that it is derived from the use of multi-source intelligence (MULTI-INT).

Information management

Information management It is the supervision, administration, regulation and timely dissemination of information. All personnel within the management process must understand the context of the information they are handling in order to effectively manage it.

Technology effect

Modern technology has revolutionized the flow of information. This provides significant new capabilities to the controller that can deliver an operational advantage by enhancing the range, speed, and volume of media, providing new formats for information, and increasing the ability to manipulate information.

Joint Intelligence, Surveillance and Reconnaissance (JISR)

It is an integrated intelligence and operations capabilities package that synchronizes and integrates the planning and operations of all acquisition capabilities with the development and dissemination of the resulting information in direct support of operations planning, preparation and execution.

There are three types of obtaining ability:

- Intelligence. The intelligence media have the ability to obtain and analyze information.
- Surveillance. It is defined as the systematic observation of airspace, surface areas or below it, places, people or things, by visual, electronic, photographic or other means. Surveillance is conducted against potential and known adversaries and threats as well as in support of operations in areas of current and potential crisis.
- Recognition. It is defined as a mission carried out to obtain, by visual observation or other methods of obtaining, information about the activities and resources of an enemy or potential enemy, or to secure data regarding the meteorological, hydrographic or geographic characteristics of a particular area.

JISR architecture.

Architecture consists of the organizations, processes and systems that connect operational intelligence and data collection units, databases, applications, generators and consumers in a joint environment.

The JISR is multidisciplinary and its intention is to extract intelligence, surveillance, and recognition of procurement capabilities into a coherent total, providing a framework for coordinating and assigning tasks to these media.

The JISR must be interoperable with other domains and functions, including their respective systems.

The organization, at all levels of command, must have the ability to: - Define the architecture necessary to efficiently execute JISR. - Articulate the CIS support necessary for the required data exchange. - Advise and find the capacities and limitations of the available JISR means against the necessary capacities. - Coordinate

between intelligence, operations, plans and CIS divisions and other relevant divisions. - Manage critical events over time..

Obtaining disciplines

Obtaining disciplines are the means or systems used to observe, sensor and record or gather information on conditions, situations, threats and events. The main disciplines of obtaining are:

- Acoustic Intelligence (ACINT) is the intelligence derived from obtaining and elaborating the acoustic phenomenon. The ACINT is mainly related to movement and intelligence that can be derived from its detection.

- Human Intelligence (HUMINT) is a category of intelligence obtained and provided by human sources. HUMINT activities encompass integrated intelligence gathering, reporting, and analysis to provide decision makers with the timely and appropriate information necessary to successfully conduct military operations.

- Image Intelligence (IMINT) is intelligence derived from images acquired with sensors that can be based on land, shipped or carried on aerial or space platforms. The information gathered in an image or in a video is clear and concise. It will often serve to support or confirm intelligence derived from other sources.

- Measurement and signature intelligence (MASINT) is intelligence and scientific and technical information obtained by the quantitative and qualitative analysis of data obtained from detection instruments in order to identify any distinctive characteristic associated with the issuing or sending source to facilitate subsequent measurement and identification. MASINT is derived from obtaining and comparison of a wide range of emissions with a known scientific and technical database in order to identify the equipment or source of the emissions.

- Open Source Intelligence (OSINT) is intelligence derived from publicly available information, as well as other unclassified information that has limited public access or distribution.

- Signal Intelligence (SIGINT) is intelligence derived from obtaining and exploiting foreign signals or emissions. This term is used when it is not necessary to differentiate between communications intelligence (COMINT) and electronic intelligence (ELINT), which are defined as:
 - o COMINT is intelligence derived from electromagnetic communications and communication systems by non-users or intended recipients.
 - o ELINT is intelligence derived from electromagnetic transmissions that are not communications by non-users or intended recipients.

Intelligence products

Specialized intelligence products include, but are not limited to governments

- Intelligence related to CBRN (Chemical, Biological, Radiological and Nuclear). - Forensic and biometric intelligence.
- Geospatial Intelligence.
- Medical Intelligence.
- Scientific and technical intelligence (STI).
- Technical Intelligence (TECHINT)
- Security Intelligence (SI). - Target intelligence.

Geospatial information on the facts geo-referenced by geographic position and arranged in a coherent structure. It can be available in digital or analogue format.

Sociological and cultural information related to the factors of human, social and cultural geography.

These factors include population, political, economic, ethnic, social stratification, stability, public opinion, education, religion, health, history, language, values, perceptions, and behaviour.

The Intel cycle

The intelligence cycle is the sequence of activities by which information is obtained, gathered, converted into intelligence and made available to users.

They focus on four fundamental phases:

- management
- obtaining,
- elaboration
- dissemination.

It is actually a complex package of activities that comprise various cycles operating at different levels and speeds. Some tasks overlap and overlap so that they are performed concurrently rather than sequentially.

The cycle consists of four phases:

- Direction. It is defined as determining the procurement needs, planning the procurement effort, the use of orders and requests to the procurement bodies, and maintaining a continuous review of the productivity of those bodies. Leadership is the key to the intelligence process.

There are two different types of address required for the process to work: the internal and external address.

External management comes from the controls of each level and establishes the parameters of intelligence needs and objectives. Internal management comes from the senior intelligence officer to each specialized element of the intelligence agency.

- Obtaining. It is defined as the exploitation of sources by the collection agencies and the delivery of information obtained to the appropriate processing unit for intelligence production. ISR media can also contribute. The procurement activity requires close collaboration between intelligence and command organization to optimize the use of the procurement means.

- Elaboration. It is defined as the conversion of information into intelligence through the compilation, evaluation, analysis, integration and interpretation. Crafting is iterative and can generate subsequent fetch requests before intelligence diffusion.

- Diffusion. It is defined as the timely delivery of intelligence in the proper way, and by any suitable means, to those who need it. It also requires security, compliance with the complainant's needs, and a feedback mechanism.

The effective management of the intelligence cycle and the coordination of the four phases is carried out through the Intelligence Needs Management and Procurement Management (IRM & CM) process. It is necessary to point out that the intelligence needs (IR) provide the rationalization and prioritization of any intelligence activity as well as providing the detail to allow the intelligence agency to respond to the need in the most effective way.

Intelligence needs must cover the entire range of information in the PMESII spectrum.

The types of military intelligence needs are:

- Critical Command Information Needs (CCIR

- Commander's Critical Information Requirements). It is the information related to the critical areas for the success of the mission or represent a critical threat. The CCIRs cover all aspects of command, including the information needs of the own forces (FFIR), Essential Elements of Own Information (EEFI) and the Priority Intelligence Needs (PIR).

- Priority Intelligence Needs (PIR - Priority Intelligence Requirements). They are a vital part of CCIRs and are normally formulated by intelligence agencies in close collaboration with command. PIRs cover those intelligence needs for which a command has an established priority.

- Specific Intelligence Needs (SIR - Specific Intelligence Requirements). They support and complement each PIR by providing a more detailed description of the need. They are used by the intelligence agency to determine which intelligence medium, source, or discipline that can best meet the need and to identify the coordination necessary to ensure the support of the appropriate media.

- Essential Elements of Information (EEI - Essential Elements of Information). SIRs are broken down into more detailed questions known as EEIs.

The EEIs add the details to the SIRs and allow the production of a procurement task assignment list based on the intelligence procurement plan.

The joint operational area

The joint operational area is divided into three areas:

- Operations Area (AOO). It is an area defined by the head of the joint force within a joint area of operations for the conduct of specific military activities.

- Intelligence area of responsibility. It is an area assigned to a commander, in which he is responsible for providing intelligence with the means at his disposal.

- Cyberspace. Within the general Operational Environment, cyberspace transcends our concepts of political or geographic borders. Therefore, managers must consider cyberspace as an area in itself.

Security

Security is the condition achieved when designated information, material, personnel, activities and facilities are protected against espionage, sabotage, subversion and terrorism, as well as against loss or unauthorized advertising. It includes the measures implemented to protect against the security threat.

It can originate from internal or external sources. Security agencies must pay particular attention to internal threats.

The threats are categorized into:

- Terrorism. It is the illegal use, or threat of use, of force or violence against individuals or property in an attempt to coerce or intimidate governments or societies to achieve political, ethnic, religious or ideological objectives.

- Espionage. Intelligence activity directed towards the acquisition of information through clandestine methods and proscribed by the law of the country against which espionage is committed.

- Sabotage. Any unfulfilled act of a military operation, or any omission, that attempts to cause physical harm in order to aid an adversary or achieve a political goal of subversion.

- Subversion. Actions designed to weaken the military, economic or political strength of a nation, undermining the morale, loyalty or reliability of its citizens. Subversion methods may include:

a) Propaganda and agitation, demonstrations and riots, distribution of pamphlets.

b) Use of undercover organizations to cover up actual activities.

c) Recruitment of followers who operate consciously or unconsciously on behalf of their recruiters.

d) The creation of a climate of mistrust and disillusionment, which is aimed at discrediting the government or individuals.

e) The spread of false rumours or distortion of the truth (disinformation) in order to destroy trust in leaders or allies.

- Organized crime. Any company, or group of people, engaged in continuous illegal activities that have the main purpose of generating profits, without respecting national borders.

- Attacks on computer networks. Actions carried out using computer networks to break, deny, degrade or destroy the information residing in computer and computer networks, or the networks and computers themselves

Responsibility to neutralize the threat.

Responsibilities of the security agency.

- Advise the command on all security threats.

- Manage and support operations to neutralize security threats.

- Obtain, develop and disseminate information regarding IC needs and produce and disseminate assessments of the current threat.
- Contribute to the operational safety process, including the planning, coordination and application of protective safety measures throughout the training.
- Establish and maintain contact with the civil security forces and the counter intelligence authorities.

Need to know. The fundamental principle of security is that knowledge or possession of classified information should be strictly limited to those, with security authorization at the appropriate level, who clearly have a need to know in order to carry out their duties. No person is authorized by virtue of their rank or position to access classified information. Reinforcing the need-to-know principle limits the damage that can be done by an internal threat, while failing to do so seriously damages security.

Principles that govern security operations

- Managers at all levels are responsible for security.
- Security operations must be coordinated with the intelligence agency, and consulted with operations and others, and integrated with the overall intelligence effort.
- They should be an individual approach at each command level for security policy.
- Security teams must be established to deal with threats and provide security advice to managers at each command level.
- The threat to information must be produced by intelligence and security personnel such as warnings, threat assessments and establishments of the threat level. These should be delivered with the lowest security rating and spread as widely as possible. - Obtaining information security must be coordinated at each command level and integrated into the overall intelligence effort.
- The responsibility for establishing and maintaining security intelligence databases should be clearly defined and, whenever possible, integrated with the overall intelligence effort.

Safety protection

Protective security is defined as the organized system of defensive measures instituted and maintained at all levels of command in order to achieve and maintain security. There are four categories of protective security measures:

- Personal Security. Those measures taken to exclude or restrict access to protect information or material from people whose loyalty, reliability or trust in them may be questionable.
- Physical security. The part of security related to physical security measures designed to safeguard personnel, prevent unauthorized access to equipment, facilities, material and documents and safeguard them against espionage, sabotage, damage and theft.
- Security in operations. Process that gives a military operation or exercise the appropriate security using active or passive means to deny an enemy the knowledge of the dispositions, capacities or intentions of the own forces.
- Information security (INFOSEC). It is defined as the necessary measures to preserve the confidentiality, integrity and availability of the information in documents, recordings or digital formats.

The objectives of security protection are:

- Reveal any attempt to penetrate the controls by unauthorized personnel.
- Prevent hostile intelligence services or subversive, terrorist or criminal organizations, groups or individuals from acquiring information, causing disruption or subverting civilian or military personnel.
- Provide a minimum of common security standards that can be applied in all formations or units.
- Prevent the possibility of unauthorized access to digital information and the destruction or alteration of information in communication or information systems or in personal computers.
- Assist in specialized investigation of security leaks.

No single security measure will be effective on its own, therefore, security and protection should consist of a number of interrelated and mutually supportive measures that together achieve an acceptable degree of security.

The application of protective security measures is primarily a national responsibility.

Development of a threat assessment.

An assessment of the threat is vital to neutralize it and must be thoroughly prepared ...

- Studying the probable strengths, capacities, methods and intentions of all the respective organizations, groups, individuals and media as mentioned before.
- Defining the possible objectives and the most likely to be attacked.

- Considering the threat to, and the vulnerability of, critical targets.

Protection force

Force Protection are the measures and means to minimize the vulnerability of personnel, facilities, material, operations and activities, to threats and damage in order to preserve freedom of action and operational effectiveness and thus contribute to the success of the mission. .

Counterintelligence

Counterintelligence are those activities related to the identification and neutralization of the security threat posed by hostile intelligence organizations or services or by individuals related to espionage, sabotage, subversion or terrorism.

The core idea of the intelligence effort is to protect personnel, information, plans and resources, nationwide and deployed. Its purpose is to provide knowledge and understanding of the prevailing situation to keep inside information secret, equipment safe, and staff safe. Counterintelligence must be proactive and preventive in its approach.

Counterintelligence is an intelligence function that provides managers at all levels with detailed knowledge of threats, vulnerabilities and risks to enable them to make well-reasoned decisions about security measures.

The command must deny the adversary the opportunity to carry out terrorism, espionage, subversion, sabotage, organized crime or attacks on the networks against their own forces.

To achieve this, it is necessary to identify the vulnerabilities of the forces inherent to the intelligence gathering operations of an adversary. This information is used to inform OPSEC's plans, against surveillance and disappointment, including the Protection Security policy.

Counterintelligence (CI) objectives.

Once the CI assessment has been completed and the security implications have been identified, the CI objectives can be identified. These are CI or intelligence facilities, organizations, information networks and personnel of interest that must be detained, destroyed, exploited or protected.

Security Implications. Intelligence and security agencies can deduce from the CI assessment the effects that the threats identified within the assessment can have on the activity of their own forces.

The implications are categorized into:

- Threats that are resolved through compliance with effective security measures and OPSEC.
- Threats (that can turn into opportunities) to be exploited by satisfying intelligence needs and conducting information operations.

Countermeasures.

These are:

- Deterrence. Robust measures will constitute an effective deterrent against a potential attacker.
- Denial. The activities applied to prevent an adversary from accessing protected and sensitive information.
- Detection. Exposing and neutralizing the opponent's efforts to gather information.
- Disappointment. Activities primarily used to mislead or confuse the adversary about the capabilities and intentions of one's own forces.

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